

“A comparative study of customer satisfaction towards service quality of ICICI Prudential and LIC at Indore City

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Abstract:

The Indian Life Insurance sector has witnessed a major revamp in 1999 with the establishment of Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority (IRDA) and subsequent entry of Private sector players. These changes are affecting the way service is being delivered. Technology usage, new innovative product introduction and competition are seen as drivers of quality of service being provided to the customers. In this study using SERVQUAL model, we have examined the importance of service based on the 5 dimensions Tangibles, Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance and Empathy. Using 100 Life Insurance policy holders from 2 Life insurance companies in Indore City. The study identified that the gaps exist even after 15 years of privatization of this sector. The study indicated that a lot needs to be done for improving customer focus and services activity in the Life Insurance sector. Regular customer surveys with increased sample sizes across the country will enable the Insurance companies to fill the gaps. The study also reveals that real growth in life insurance will occur when customers realize the true value of life insurance beyond tax saving.

INTRODUCTION

The insurance companies of our country perform a wide range of activities such as service designing, preparing contract and policy, marketing and selling, underwriting, rating, reinsurance and other services and claim settlement.

There were also allegations of unfair trade practices being prevalent to a great extent. The Government of India, therefore, decided to standardize and nationalize the practice of insurance business. As for knowing the customer satisfaction & service qualities we have read various journals, research paper, case studies which are given in further literature review so that the study will be specific

In 1956 nationalization of insurance business was a major milestone in the development of insurance business in India by taking 245 private insurers business. The Indian insurance market was thrown open to private players in the year 1999 and the Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority (IRDA) was established to regulate the insurance market.

The Product

Life Insurance is now the most popular instrument for the planning for the risk of untimely death, the concept has been modified to merge with saving vehicles to create very interesting and apt investment product. Life insurance products have to suit the requirements of customer. The three major concerns of any person could be-Dying too early, living too long Or Living with disability Life insurance products fundamentally provide for-

1. Risk Cover
2. Investment
3. Health Cover,
4. Tax saving

There are four main types of insurance policies described as follows.-

1. Term Insurance: Term Insurance pays a death benefit to the legal heirs if the person insured, dies during the term of the policy. Terms insurance plans offer pure risk cover without any element of saving.

2. Whole Life Insurance: The advantage of whole life insurance is that the policy, if kept current, covers you over your entire life, as opposed to term insurance that covers you only for a certain term of years.

3. Endowment Insurance: Pure endowment is a plan where the benefit is payable to the insured only on survival of the specified term.

4. Annuities: Annuities are a form of pension in which an insurance company makes a series of periodic payments to a person or his or her dependents over a numbers of years, in return for the money paid to the insurance company either in lump or installments.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Service is “an activity, benefit, or satisfaction offered for sale that is essentially intangible and does not result in the ownership of anything.” There are certain characteristics of services distinct from goods such as: (i) Intangibility (i.e. services cannot be tasted, seen, heard, smelled, felt) (ii) Inseparability (simultaneous production and consumption) (iii) Heterogeneity (service quality depends on who provides service, when, where and how) (iv) Perishability, i.e. services cannot be inventoried (Kotler and Armstrong, 2012).

Arulsuresh (2011) suggested that the success of the life insurance business depends on the awareness of the policyholders about the products and satisfaction of the policyholders regarding the service rendered by LIC of India. Life insurance being a service sector is no exception to this principle. The basics of Customer Relations Management (CRM) include a business strategy that focuses on developing and retaining the relationships existing between customer and organization. CRM also provides the customer with a much needed avenue to find expression for his problems, ideas and suggestions. Hundreds of sales leads are lost yearly as disinterested employees pay slack attention to customer suggestions. A venue is required for these suggestions.

Borah (2012) explained that the modern concept of marketing emphasizes on the satisfaction of customers. Marketing begins and end with the customers. Customers are the King in business. The study analysis the service quality perception of 50 customers in Jorhat, Assam chosen from Kotak Mahindra Life Insurance Company to access their satisfaction level and also identify service factors which have the maximum impact on customers’ satisfaction. For choosing the sample, non-probabilistic judgment-cum-convenience sampling technique was used. The finding of the study shows that most of the customers are satisfied.

Rao (2014) explained that liberalization of the financial services sector has led to insurance companies functioning increasingly under competitive pressures; so companies are consequently directing their strategies towards increasing customer satisfaction and loyalty through improved service quality. With the opening of insurance industry to private players, the competition has intensified and it has become very difficult for the companies to attract and retain the policyholders. Every company has recognized the need for shifting from a traditional strategy to survive in the market. It is in this context, the process of CRM has been adopted by all private and public sector insurance companies as well.

According to him overall retail image is influenced by store location, merchandise attributes, pricing, firm’s positioning, customer service, target market, attributes of physical facilities, shopping experience, promotion tools (such as advertising, public relations, personal selling, sales promotion) and community service. Further, he noted that a retailer’s image depends heavily on its ‘atmosphere’ or the psycho-logical feeling a customer gets when in that retail outlet. Liping (2005) revised the RSQS for the Chinese customer and retail stores, considering the customer characteristics and china cultural background, they retained five dimensions of the original model, but the scale items have been adjusted, the number of variables was reduced from 28 to 22, of which 19 variables came from RSQS, and added three new variables. Tam (2005) explained that it is important for success in influencing customer satisfaction to understand how customer expectations develops and update even if the term expectation is vague and difficult to interpret in surveys. Gibson (2005) found in his studies that satisfied customers become repeat purchasers of a product or service and provide

positive word of mouth. That means that it is important to understand what factors that influences customer satisfaction in order to create good products or services. Zhao (2007) introduced 24 variables in the paper “an empirical research on Retail Service Quality Evaluation” for the case of supermarket service. He published the paper “an empirical study on customer service quality and relationship quality based on the interactive model”, clearly discussed the relation and influence between the interaction quality and customer service quality, but no scale was formed. Lovelock and Wirtz (2007) described that the nature of service quality requires a distinctive approach to indentify and measure service quality. Because customers are often involved in service production, a distinction needs to be drawn between the process of service delivery and the actual output of the service which is called technical quality. Other researchers suggest that the perceived quality of service is the result of an evaluation process in which customers compare their perceptions of service delivery with the expected outcome. Grönroos (2007) suggested that in order to increase long term quality, the customer expectations should be focused, revealed, and calibrated and he also developed the dynamic model of expectation that describes that the quality of professional services develops in a customer relationship over time (<http://www.scribd.com>., 2012).

This model classifies the expectations into three distinguishable types and can be characterized in the following; (a) Fuzzy expectations exist when customers expect a service provider to solve a problem but do not have a clear understanding of what should be done. (b) Explicit expectations are clear in the customer’s minds in advance of the service process. They can be divided into realistic and unrealistic expectations. (c) Implicit expectations refer to element of a service which are so obvious to customers that they do not consciously think about them but take them for granted”. Fiore and Kim (2007) presented a conceptual framework that concerns the influences on the consumption experience by environmental variables such as physical elements of the service environment, individual variables, individual attributes and person-environment variables or situations. The physical environment has the possibility to provide ideas about the influence of customer perceptions on the brand image. Lovelock and Wirtz (2007) discussed how confirmation or disconfirmation of expectations relates to satisfaction and delight: The terms quality and satisfaction are sometimes used interchangeably. Lovelock and Wirtz (2007) explained that a service encounter is a period of time during which the customer interact directly with the service provider. Some of these encounters are very brief and consist of just a few steps. If you use a service that requires the customer to make a reservation this first step might have been taken days or even weeks before the customer arrives at the service facility. They also discussed the SERVQUAL Model. It is static and describes a single service encounter or moment of truth. Service processes usually consist of a series of encounters, such as your experience with a flight that consist of steps from making reservation to checking in, taking the flight, and retrieving customer’s bags on arrival. Knowledge of role and script theories can help us to understand, design, and manage both customer behavior and employee behavior during those encounters. Strickland (2008) noted that customers have two levels of expectations: desired and acceptable levels. She further advised that for an organization to achieve the range between acceptable and desired, it has to establish: product and service quality specifications, employee performance metrics, product performance and quality metrics, clear definitions of customer expectations, service process management, service

process metrics, on-going interactive customer orientation, iterative process monitoring, controls and corrective action procedures.

Zeithaml et al., (2009) argued that perceptions of service quality are the results of customer's comparisons of expected service with perceived service. They contend that the gaps between expected and actual/delivered service creates dissatisfaction. Thus, the retailers challenge is to minimize the gaps between expected and actual by first understanding customers' expectation and then delivering those expectations.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To asses service quality of ICICI Prudential & LIC insurance company.
- To asses customer satisfaction of ICICI Prudential & LIC Insurance company.
- To study & compare various plans offered by LIC & ICICI Prudential insurance company.
- To compare customer satisfaction for ICICI Prudential & LIC insurance company.

HYPOTHESIS

H₀: There is no significance difference of service quality of ICICI Prudential insurance & LIC at Indore.

H₀: There is no significance difference of customer satisfaction for ICICI Prudential insurance & LIC at Indore.

H₁: There is significance difference of service quality of ICICI Prudential insurance & LIC at Indore.

H₂: There is significance difference of customer satisfaction for ICICI Prudential insurance & LIC at Indore.

RESEARCH DESIGN

The study uses the exploratory & conclusive design to determine the customer satisfaction of ICICI Prudential & LIC insurance company

SAMPLE DESIGN

1. Sampling Population:-Population we will include the customers who are living at Indore region.

2. Sampling unit: - customers.

Secondary data: - Text books, national as well as international articles and diaries annual report of LIC & ICICI Prudential.

3. Sample size:-100

DATA COLLECTION METHOD:-By visiting customers in insurance company.

DATA ANALYSIS METHOD: - Convenience sampling (non probability sampling technique) for achieving the objective of customer satisfaction for LIC & ICICI prudential. Several model for fulfilling the objective of service quality of ICICI Prudential & LIC insurance company. ANOVA test for examining the hypothesis.

Table 1: Reliability Coefficient for Dimensions of Service Quality

Name of Insurance Company	Number of Items	Cronbach.s Alpha
LIC	23	0.966
ICICI Prudential	23	0.956
Overall	23	0.961

Table 2: Scores on the SERVQUAL Scale

No	Dimensions of Servqual	Insurance Company	
		LIC	ICICI Prudential
1	Tangibility	4.40	3.78
2	Reliability	4.78	3.37
3	Responsiveness	4.74	3.70
4	Assurance	4.80	3.82
5	Empathy	4.72	3.74

Table 3: Average Scores for Five Service Quality Dimensions (Question Wi

Q.no	Tangibility		Reliability		Responsiveness		Assurance		Empathy	
	LIC	ICICI	LIC	ICICI	LIC	ICICI	LIC	ICICI	LIC	ICICI
1	4.37	3.69	4.63	3.52	4.95	3.82	4.82	3.71	4.85	3.91
2	4.53	3.85	4.60	3.44	4.65	3.70	485	3.78	4.77	3.390
3	4.37	3.98	4.71	3.09	4.76	3.63	476	3.94	4.67	3.54
4	4.33	3.62	4.89	3.23	4.59	3.67	480	3.83	4.67	3.60
5	-	-	5.08	3.55	-	-			4.62	3.72

Correlation Analysis

Factor	R.Value
Tangibility	0.970
Reliability	0.972
Responsiveness	0.970
Assurance	0.967
Empathy	0.969

Table 4a: Correlation Coefficient for ICICI

Factor	.R. Value
Tangibility	0.973
Reliability	0.945
Responsiveness	0.956
Assurance	0.967
Empathy	0.965

Regression Analysis

Table 5: Regression Analysis for ICICI Prudential

ICICI Prudential			
Overall service quality = 0.583(Empathy) + 0.459(Tangibles) + 0.304 (Responsiveness) + 0.211 Assurance			
(0.069)	(0.069)	(0.069)	(0.069)
+ 0.192 (Reliability)			
(0.069)			
R2 = 0.725			

Table 6: Regression Analysis for LIC

LIC			
Overall service quality = 0.630(Empathy) + 0.475(Tangibles) + 0.386 (Responsiveness)+0.337(Assurance)			
(0.031)	(0.031)	(0.031)	(0.031)
+ 0.207 (Reliability)			
(0.031)			
R2 = 0.928			

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Table 7: Comparison of Beta Coefficients

Dimension	LIC	ICICI Prudential
	Beta Coefficient Values	Beta Coefficient Values
Tangibility	0.207	0.459
Reliability	0.475	0.192
Responsiveness	0.337	0.304
Assurance	0.386	0.215
Empathy	0.630	0.583

Statistically, it is being observed that the beta coefficient values for reliability, assurance dimensions are higher in case of LIC as compared to ICICI Prudential. Whereas, only one dimension tangibility got statistically higher beta coefficient value for ICICI Prudential.

Hypothesis Testing

In this research the hypothesis testing is being done with the use of t- test. The results of t- test are as follows:

Table 8: Group Statistics

Group Statistics					
	VAR00002	N	MEAN	S.D.	S.E. for Mean
VAR00001	LIC	5	4.6880	0.16459	0.07361
ICICI		3.6811	0.18166	0.08124	

Table 9: t - Test

	Levene.s Tes means for Variances							t . test for equality of Equality of	
								95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
VAR00001	F	Sig	T	Df	Sig. (2 . tailed)	Mean Difference	SE Difference	Lowar	Upper
Equal Var	0.027	0.875	9.185		0.000	1.00690	0.10963	0.75410	1.25970

Levene.s test for equality of variances shows that F value is insignificant, so assumption of equal variances is accepted. With this evidence, t .test for equality of means is conducted, and result show that t value is laying outside the confidence interval. Therefore the null hypothesis is rejected. It is being proved that there is a difference in the service quality perceptions of customers in the public and private sector insurance companies

Conclusion

As the government of India has opened the insurance sector for private sector so the competition has increased and the companies want to differentiate themselves from the competitors and stay ahead in the race. The oldest and leading public sector company in the insurance sector is LIC which is now facing a very tough competition from the private sector companies. On the one front LIC is facing lot of competition and on the second front there is a decline in the market share. At the same time, they should also make sure that the service quality dimensions like Reliability and empathy in which they are doing well are given their due importance. In case of the insurance sector word of mouth plays a vital role so the leading insurance companies should give due consideration to the service quality. In order to get the competitive advantage over the competitors the service quality should be used as a strategic tool. In order to strengthen the level of the service quality LIC should focus on assurance and tangibility. In this cut throat competition it is cheaper to retain the customer rather than finding a new customer. Being a major player LIC has to concentrate more on retaining a customer rather than finding a new customer. The existing players can focus on the various service quality dimensions to create a competitive advantage, which is sustainable and which cannot be easily matched by their new competitors in the long run.

In case of the private insurance companies, they are competing in the market very aggressively. But the low score for reliability dimension is not a good signal for them. Private players need to focus on the reliability part, and at the same time, since they are good at tangibles, they should leverage it for their rapid growth. Assurance is also one area they need to focus, so that customers can be satisfied.

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